

Methods of Applying Interactive Methods of Education to Students in Developed Foreign Countries

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Abstract: *In this article, one of the effective teaching technologies in the educational system of developed countries is problem-based teaching. Problem teaching corresponds to the goals of creative and active personality education. The essence of problem-based learning is independent assimilation of new knowledge by creating a problem situation.*

Keywords — Education, modern knowledge, pedagogical experience, interactive methods, pedagogical technologies, educational process, activity, purpose.

INTRODUCTION.

Today, the main goal of higher education is to form spiritually rich individuals who have acquired modern knowledge, have the ability to think independently and solve problems. As the society develops, the level of living requirements also increases. So, as the volume of knowledge expands and the level of scientific knowledge deepens, the demand for logical thinking and quick problem solving also increases. From this point of view, we come to the conclusion that the educational system needs to determine and take into account not only today's requirements, but also future requirements. Because today's requirements will become the main core of society in the future. Therefore, it is necessary that the education system prepares students not for the life of today, but for the life of the future. This is also one of the unique features of education.

In pedagogical experience and practice, the term "active forms and methods of teaching" has been used for a long time. This term combines pedagogical technologies that bring the active learning activity of students to higher levels. In today's educational era, another new term, "interactive learning", has become widespread.

The modern science of education has reached such a period that there is an urgent need for the emergence of new pedagogical technologies that allow the development of the personality of each student and his activity. In the educational process, it is necessary to create such conditions of teaching, in which it is very important that the student strives to obtain effective results from his work and can successfully apply them in his further practical work.

Today, we should think and worry about what the future holds for our students. One thing is clear to us, the future requires from them not only a huge stock of knowledge in their chosen specialty, but also knowledge of modern technologies.

Modern educational literature, various educational tools for teachers, as a result of quality training, allow to organize the lesson in such a way that students' thinking, memory, attention and other types of cognitive activities actively develop. An effectively organized lesson not only forms deep and solid

knowledge, but also forms skills such as using them in different situations, independently obtaining knowledge, and problem-solving experiences. That is why now, it is one of the important tasks to establish goal-oriented activities for the development of intellectual, physical, mental-volitional skills of students.

To get the best results in solving this problem, it is necessary to get students to actively participate in the learning process and approach it seriously.

How to organize the lesson so that the learning process is interesting for both the teacher and the student?

In order to achieve such a result, pedagogy offers training of a sense of responsibility, development of interest, adaptation of educational material to the capabilities of the student, etc.

The modern educational system requires the search and mastering of new forms of mutual educational cooperation between the participants of the educational process. In the process of such research, new, interactive teaching methods (inter-mutual, actio-movement) have been created today.

The following are the principles and goals of interactive learning:

- Principle of activity. Involve all participants in active communication, discussion and problem solving.
- The principle of feedback. Encourage discussion of arguments or objections raised.
- The principle of the experiment. Encourage the search for new ways to solve the presented problems.
- The principle of trust. Eliminating the stereotype of a strict teacher and a passive listener who receives ready-made information.
- The principle of equality of views. To express Fz's opinion on an equal basis with other participants of the educational process. The purpose of interactive education:
 - development of communication skills;
 - creating comfortable conditions and a comfortable emotional environment for all participants of the lesson; - to

develop teamwork skills and the ability to express one's thoughts;

- formation of interest in learning and internal motivation;
- development of creativity. Interactive methods of teaching are methods of interaction between all participants of the educational process, during which the students stop the passive role and are actively involved in the work. Interactive teaching technologies make the learning process in higher education institutions more interesting and effective.

According to the educational pyramid developed by the National Learning Center (Maryland, USA) in the 1980s, a person remembers only 5% of what he hears, and 90% of the information he remembers when he teaches it to others. The teaching process should be organized in such a way that the audience can absorb as much material as possible and feel comfortable.

The peculiarity of these teaching methods is that they ensure the active dominance of the audience in the learning process, the role of the teacher is reduced to the direction of their activity in order to achieve the goals of the lesson.

In addition, the teacher develops a lesson plan, often these are interactive tasks and exercises, during which the students learn the educational material.

It can be said that interactive teaching methods are a specific form of organizing demonstrative activities, implying clear and pre-planned educational goals.

The goal of interactive methods is to create favorable conditions for the listener to feel successful and intellectually mature.

The conditions created using interactive methods of teaching have a positive effect on the effectiveness of the educational process, create an environment for students to acquire knowledge and skills in a comfortable psychological environment, as well as to solve problems in the educational system. The scheme of interactive teaching methods is based on "teacher-listener" and "listener-listener" interaction schemes. These schemes involve not only the teacher, but also the interaction of the students with each other in the learning process.

The interaction between listeners and listeners helps to increase learning motivation, to show initiative in the learning process. The main tasks of interactive teaching methods:

1. To stimulate and increase the interest of the listeners in learning.
2. To improve the efficiency of study material.
3. To give listeners the opportunity to independently search for educational information, ways and options for solving the educational and scientific problem. When setting an educational problem, the teacher can offer two options for finding a solution: - the first - choosing from ready-made answers, - the second - an independent and reasonable solution to the problem.

4. Establishing mutual relations between students during the educational process, forming teamwork skills (team, group, etc.), respect and tolerance for different points of view of the participants of the educational process, respecting the right to freedom of speech and respecting the dignity of others.

5. Forming the ability of the listeners to express and defend their opinion, to argue for it.

6. Formation and development of necessary life and professional skills.

7. Formation of conscious competence of listeners.

The use of interactive forms of teaching significantly changes the role of the teacher in the educational process, he ceases to be the central person, but becomes the regulator of the process.

The task of the teacher is to prepare effective interactive educational tasks, formulate questions and topics for discussion among the audience, hold consultations and monitor the implementation of planned tasks. In the process of teaching, the teacher and students communicate with each other, solve educational problems and issues together, resolve conflicts, find common points of contact and compromise. All this implies an interactive form of education. Let's get acquainted with some methods of interactive education: Brainstorming - a stream of questions and answers to the audience or proposals on a certain topic. - Analysis of the correctness or incorrectness of the suggestions and answers is done after brainstorming. - The audience is mainly involved in the analysis, the teacher only corrects and guides. Comparative charts, clusters and puzzles. The essence of this method is that the listeners look for solutions to the main problems on the topics given to the teachers. Interactive lesson using ICT (audio and video materials). The teacher selects or independently creates test tasks on the Internet, works with electronic educational programs and websites. A roundtable discussion held in the form of a debate or discussion is a group type of method that involves collective discussion and the search for a solution to a given problem. This is done by expressing thoughts, opinions and assumptions. Business games (imitation, role) are one of the most popular methods of interactive education. During Fyjn, the audience plays certain roles depending on the given situation. Project style. This method involves independent preparation of a project on a certain topic and then defending it in front of other listeners. BarCamp or the anti-conference. The style was suggested by webmaster Tim Reilly. Its content is that all conferences can be not only a participant, but also an organizer. - All participants come up with new ideas, presentations, proposals on a certain topic. - In addition, the search for the most interesting ideas and their general discussion is carried out. Interactive teaching methods in the classroom include techniques such as workshops, brainstorming, and decision trees. All interactive methods of teaching are developed based on the requirements of State educational standards and are designed to teach the main problem - to teach the audience to

learn. That is, the information should not be provided ready-made. The development of critical thinking based on situational analysis, independent search for information, chain making, balanced and reasoned decision-making should be essential.

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